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THE JOURNAL PROVIDES INTERDISCIPLINARY ANALYSES AND A VIGOROUS EXCHANGE OF PERSPECTIVES THAT ARE ESSENTIAL TO THE UNDERSTANDING OF THE NATURE OF GLOBAL HEALTH CHALLENGES AND THE STRATEGIES AIMED AT THEIR SOLUTION. THE JOURNAL IS PARTICULARLY INTERESTED IN ADDRESSING THE POLITICAL, ECONOMIC, SOCIAL, MILITARY AND STRATEGIC ASPECTS OF GLOBAL HEALTH ISSUES.

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REFOCUSING GLOBAL HEALTH PRIORITIES: THE DYNAMICS OF AGENDA SETTING IN GLOBAL HEALTH IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH

Vivek N.D.

This paper examines the complex process of global health agenda-setting, focusing on the Global South, particularly India. It explores how various stakeholders – governments, international organizations, and civil society, shape health priorities and policies. Drawing on critical political economy and historical perspectives, the study analyzes the role of political, economic, and social factors influencing health agenda-setting. The methodology incorporates both qualitative and quantitative research methods, using a combination of primary and secondary sources to offer empirical insights. Key findings reveal a shift in global health financing dynamics, with increasing reliance on philanthrocapitalist and multi-bi funding mechanisms, diverting focus from traditional multilateral institutions like WHO. This shift raises concerns about the short-term prioritization of health issues at the expense of long-term goals, while also highlighting the growing influence of private actors on global health policy. The analysis emphasizes the importance of international norms, economic interests, and institutional frameworks in shaping health policies, particularly in low-income countries. The paper concludes by addressing the power imbalances in global health governance, underscoring the need for more inclusive and equitable approaches to health policy. It advocates for collaboration across borders and the prioritization of marginalized communities to address systemic health disparities in the Global South.

INTRODUCTION

Global health priorities have undergone profound shifts over the past two decades, shaped by the emergence of new financing mechanisms, political agendas and economic interests. A major turning point has been the rise of vertical funding mechanisms like the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis, and Malaria (GFATM) and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation's (BMGF) large-scale interventions. These actors, along with other private philanthropies and international organizations, have significantly influenced the global health landscape, particularly in the Global South. One key aspect of this shift is how global health financing has become more project-oriented, often focused on specific diseases rather than strengthening overall health systems. For instance, the focus on combating HIV/AIDS through vertical programs has often diverted attention from broader systemic issues like healthcare infrastructure and workforce development. While disease-specific funding has brought much-needed resources to countries like India, it has also led to an imbalance in health priorities, where systemic reforms are sidelined in favor of short-term gains in disease reduction.

In India, the influence of these global health priorities is particularly evident. The country has been a recipient of substantial funding from international organizations like the Global Fund and Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance. However, this influx of resources has also sparked debates around health sovereignty and agenda-setting. The Indian government, while engaging with global health actors, has had to navigate

tensions between externally driven priorities and domestic health needs. For example, India's emphasis on universal health coverage under the Ayushman Bharat program contrasts with the more disease-specific focus of global health donors. This creates a complex interplay between local and global actors in shaping health policies.

Moreover, global health agenda-setting in the Global South often reflects broader geopolitical and economic realities. In the case of India, the country's growing economic power and political influence have enabled it to play a more assertive role in global health governance. India's leadership in advocating for affordable generic drugs during the HIV/AIDS crisis in the early 2000s is a prime example of its ability to shape global health narratives in favor of equity and access, even as powerful pharmaceutical companies and Western governments pushed for stringent intellectual property protections under the WTO's TRIPS agreement.

Beyond governments and international organizations, civil society has also played a critical role in shaping health policies in the Global South. In India, civil society organizations have been pivotal in advocating for equitable access to healthcare, particularly in areas neglected by both the government and international donors. For instance, grassroots movements such as the Jan Swasthya Abhiyan (People's Health Movement) have pushed for better access to maternal and child health services in rural areas, which often fall outside the purview of global health programs focused on urban centers and more "visible" health crises.

However, the growing influence of private sector actors, including philanthropic organizations, raises questions about accountability and the broader implications for health equity. In many cases, the priorities of these actors reflect neoliberal ideologies that prioritize efficiency and market-based solutions, sometimes at the expense of addressing social determinants of health and structural inequities. For example, while digital health solutions are being promoted as a way to improve access to healthcare in rural India, these technologies often fail to address the underlying issues of poverty, education and infrastructure that limit their effectiveness.

The institutional frameworks guiding global health governance also play a critical role in determining whose interests are prioritized. The World Health Organization (WHO), despite being the primary international body for global health, has seen its influence wane in favor of donor-driven institutions. This shift has significant implications for countries like India, where health challenges are deeply rooted in social inequalities and require holistic, long-term solutions rather than fragmented, disease-specific interventions.

In sum, the process of global health agenda-setting in the Global South, and particularly in India, is shaped by a complex web of actors and interests. Governments, international organizations and civil society each play a role in shaping health policies, but power imbalances, economic incentives and institutional priorities often skew the agenda in ways that undermine health equity and social justice. By understanding these dynamics, we can better advocate for health policies that truly reflect the needs of marginalized populations and promote more just and inclusive health systems.

GLOBAL HEALTH AGENDA SETTING: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Global health agenda-setting refers to the process by which certain health issues rise to prominence in international forums and shape national policies. Traditionally, governments, international organizations like the WHO, and increasingly, private actors such as philanthrocapitalists (e.g., the BMGF) play key roles in defining these priorities. According to Kingdon's¹ agenda-setting theory, certain issues rise to

prominence due to the convergence of problem recognition, policy proposals and political will, often termed “windows of opportunity.” These windows open when issues gain enough attention due to crises, changes in the political landscape or shifts in public opinion.

In the Global South, agenda-setting in health is more complex. The legacy of colonialism, coupled with deep economic and political disparities, heavily influences how health priorities are established. Scholars such as Sen, Qadeer, and Missoni² point out that many health policies in the Global South are still shaped by post-colonial dynamics, where external actors, often from the Global North, have a significant influence on policy formulation. For example, global health initiatives such as the Global Fund and Gavi have provided substantial funding to countries like India, but these funds often come with predetermined priorities, pushing governments to focus on specific diseases like HIV/AIDS or malaria, sometimes at the expense of broader health system strengthening.

Under Prime Minister Narendra Modi’s leadership, India has made significant strides in combating infectious diseases, particularly tuberculosis, with a commitment to eliminate TB by 2025³. India, one of the largest recipients of Global Fund grants, has received over US\$2.36 billion since 2003 to fight TB, HIV, and malaria⁴. Each year, the Global Fund invests at least US\$ 600 million in India to procure essential health supplies, including HIV medications, mosquito nets and diagnostic kits⁵. These critical resources support the country’s efforts in controlling and eradicating diseases such as HIV/AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis. It must be noted that, India has been making significant strides toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), outpacing the global average. Between 2015 and 2022, the country achieved a 16% reduction in tuberculosis incidence, from 237 per 100,000 population to 199, alongside an 18% decrease in TB-related deaths during this period⁶. This progress reflects India’s robust efforts in combating infectious diseases and strengthening its healthcare system. In 2023, Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance, and the Government of India partnered on a new three-year initiative to deliver life-saving vaccines to millions of children. Gavi will contribute US\$ 250 million to identify unvaccinated children and introduce the HPV and typhoid conjugate vaccines into India’s routine immunization program⁷. Further, the BMGF Annual Report 2023 states it had invested US\$ 123 million in India out of the total US \$ 1.86 billion allocated to global health⁸.

This external influence can create a situation where governments are in a reactive position, responding to global priorities rather than setting their own. In India, for instance, while international funding has helped tackle specific health challenges, it has also led to fragmented health policies that sometimes neglect systemic issues such as healthcare access, workforce development and infrastructure improvement⁹. As a result, local health needs—particularly in rural and marginalized communities—are often overshadowed by donor-driven priorities that focus on more “visible” health crises.

The recent COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the agenda-setting power of external actors. Global priorities around vaccination and pandemic preparedness have been shaped by multilateral organizations like the WHO, alongside private sector and philanthropic players. While these efforts have been crucial in addressing the global pandemic, they have also raised concerns about equity in access to vaccines and healthcare resources. In India, the initial vaccine rollout underscored the disparities between urban and rural areas, with wealthier regions receiving more resources while marginalized groups faced delays in access¹⁰. This dynamic illustrates how agenda-setting can sometimes exacerbate existing inequalities within national health systems.

Moreover, the growing influence of private actors in global health agenda-setting has led to the rise of philanthrocapitalism. This phenomenon, where wealthy individuals or organizations wield significant influence over public health priorities, has reshaped how global health policies are formulated. Scholars like Storeng and de Bengy Puyvallée¹¹ argue that while philanthrocapitalism brings much-needed resources to global health, it can also narrow the focus of health interventions, prioritizing technological solutions over long-term systemic change.

Thus, global health agenda-setting is a complex process shaped by various stakeholders, each with their own interests and influence. In the Global South, these dynamics are further complicated by historical legacies of inequality, economic dependence and external pressures. For countries like India, the challenge lies in balancing external health priorities with local needs, ensuring that global health interventions promote equity and sustainability in their health systems. Recent scholarship and the COVID-19 pandemic underscore the importance of local leadership and inclusive governance in setting health agendas that truly reflect the needs of the most vulnerable populations.

INDIA AS A CASE STUDY

India's role in global health is significant due to its size, population, and geopolitical influence¹². It is home to a significant portion of the global disease burden, including non-communicable diseases (NCDs), infectious diseases, and malnutrition. In India, febrile illnesses are commonly caused by diseases such as dengue, malaria, typhoid, and tuberculosis. India holds the highest global burden of tuberculosis, accounting for 27% of the world's TB cases¹³. By contrast, Global South countries such as Indonesia contributes around 10% of the global TB burden, while Nigeria carries 4.5%, both reflecting high incidence relative to their smaller populations¹⁴. India ranks third globally in terms of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) burden¹⁵. In terms of absolute numbers South Africa accounts for the highest HIV burden with a total HIV prevalence among the population from 15-49 years at 17.8%¹⁶. India has the highest number of undernourished people globally, with 194.6 million suffering from inadequate nutrition¹⁷. Yet, the country has also become a leader in health innovation and public health interventions, particularly in vaccine production and distribution, as seen in the COVID-19 pandemic.

However, India's health agenda is shaped not only by domestic needs but also by international influences. The government's health priorities, such as the National Health Policy¹⁸ and Ayushman Bharat¹, reflect a blend of national interests and global health imperatives. International financial institutions (IFIs) such as the International Monetary Fund and World Bank as well as philanthropic foundations such as the BMGF have played a significant role in shaping India's health agenda. Through partnerships with government agencies and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), BMGF has supported initiatives in maternal and child health, sanitation and disease control¹⁹.

Similarly, in Africa the legal and regulatory conditions for greater participation of IFIs and private actors have been laid on the ground in many countries. The World Bank Group has especially promoted public-private partnerships (PPPs) in healthcare across Africa, embedding financialization into health systems²⁰. This shift often

¹ Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PM-JAY) is a public health insurance scheme by the Government of India aimed at providing free healthcare coverage to low-income individuals, specifically targeting the bottom 50% of the population.

undermines universal healthcare goals in the Global South by prioritizing market logics over public health needs.

India's health policy landscape exemplifies the growing influence of private and international actors in shaping health priorities in the Global South. This has resulted in a shift away from traditional multilateral institutions like the WHO toward more flexible, multi-bi² funding arrangements²¹.

THE SHIFT FROM MULTILATERALISM TO PHILANTHROCAPITALISM

One of the most significant changes in global health governance is the rise of philanthrocapitalism. Foundations such as BMGF, Bloomberg Philanthropies, and Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance, have become major players in global health. These organizations often operate outside traditional multilateral structures, focusing instead on targeted initiatives and public-private partnerships. Philanthrocapitalist entities are now increasingly major contributors to global health aid, accounting for at least 20% of the total since 2000²² – a substantial portion of the overall funding for health interventions in low- and middle-income countries.

This shift in funding dynamics has both positive and negative implications. On one hand, philanthrocapitalist organizations have introduced innovation and flexibility into global health financing²³. They can mobilize resources quickly and implement targeted interventions, often addressing gaps left by more bureaucratic multilateral organizations. On the other hand, there are concerns that their priorities may not always align with national needs. Philanthrocapitalists are often criticized for prioritizing high-visibility, short-term interventions over long-term health systems strengthening²⁴.

The BMGF has played a pivotal role in global health, particularly in the fight against polio. As of 2023, polio cases have been reduced by over 99% since the launch of global eradication initiatives in 1988, and BMGF's efforts have been central to this progress, contributing billions of dollars to the cause²⁵. However, critics argue that this narrow focus has drawn attention and resources away from other significant public health challenges in the Global South, such as malnutrition and maternal mortality. For instance, malnutrition remains a significant issue in countries like India, where an estimated 35.5% of children under five are stunted and 19.3% are wasted, according to UNICEF's 2023 data²⁶. Meanwhile, maternal mortality rates in low-income countries remain high, with an estimated 536 deaths per 100,000 live births in sub-Saharan Africa in 2020²⁷, underscoring the need for broader health interventions beyond disease-specific initiatives.

Similarly, Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance, has been instrumental in expanding vaccine access across the Global South, with over 1.1 billion children worldwide having received immunizations between 2000 and 2023²⁸. However, its emphasis on vaccine distribution has sparked debate about the neglect of broader health system strengthening, such as improving healthcare infrastructure and workforce capacity. While Gavi's efforts have ensured that millions of children receive life-saving vaccines, some health experts argue that without sustainable investments in primary healthcare systems, these gains may not be enduring²⁹. For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic, fragile health systems in many low-income countries struggled to respond

² Funding allocated to multilateral organisations for designated purposes, sectors, regions, or countries, including contributions to trust funds and collaborative initiatives, is termed "multi-bi" aid. In other words, multi-bi aid refers to all designated voluntary donations to multilateral organizations, which are often made through specific trust accounts and fall beyond the core financing.

effectively, highlighting the need for more comprehensive health system reforms alongside targeted vaccination efforts³⁰.

These examples illustrate the tension between disease-specific interventions and the broader goal of strengthening health systems to address the root causes of health disparities in the Global South. While the contributions of organizations like BMGF and Gavi are undeniable, the sustainability and equity of global health efforts hinge on a more holistic approach that integrates systemic improvements with targeted health initiatives.

In India, philanthrocapitalism has significantly influenced health policy. BMGF, for instance, has partnered with the Indian government on several initiatives, including polio eradication, maternal and child health, and sanitation under the Swachh Bharat mission³¹. These partnerships have had a profound impact on health outcomes in the country, but they have also raised concerns about accountability and transparency. On a side note, in India too private philanthropy is on the rise. The sector grew by 10% in FY 2023, reaching US\$15 billion³².

SHIFT FROM MULTILATERAL FUNDING TO MULTI-BI FINANCING

While the involvement of philanthropic organizations has accelerated progress in some areas, there is a risk that health priorities are being driven by donor interests rather than local needs³³. This highlights the importance of ensuring that philanthrocapitalist funding aligns with national health strategies and priorities. Further, multi-bi financing, where donors channel their contributions toward specific projects through multilateral institutions, has had a profound impact on global health agenda-setting. This approach allows donors, such as governments or private foundations, to earmark funds for particular health priorities, often aligned with their own strategic interests. However, this targeted funding can distort the broader health agenda by sidelining underfunded but crucial areas of health, particularly long-term challenges faced by low-income countries.

A key example of this phenomenon is the WHO. While WHO's overall budget has increased over the years, largely due to earmarked contributions from donors, its core budget has remained relatively stagnant. According to WHO's 2022–2023 budget data, only 16% of the organization's funding was derived from assessed contributions (unrestricted core funding), while the remaining 84% came from voluntary contributions, much of which was earmarked for specific initiatives such as polio eradication, COVID-19 response and immunization programs³⁴. This heavy reliance on earmarked funds limits the WHO's ability to direct resources toward broader, long-term health system strengthening and primary healthcare, which are critical for addressing health inequities in low-income countries.

The consequences of this funding model are visible in the underfunding of global health initiatives such as health workforce development and the fight against non-communicable diseases (NCDs). For example, WHO reported in 2022 that nearly 10 million more healthcare workers would be needed by 2030 to meet Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with the most severe shortages occurring in low- and middle-income countries³⁵. However, only a fraction of the WHO's budget is allocated to support health workforce development, as donor priorities often focus on disease-specific interventions such as vaccines or pandemic preparedness³⁶.

Similarly, while NCDs account for 74% of global deaths or 41 million people annually³⁷, funding for NCD prevention and treatment remains inadequate, particularly in low-income countries where healthcare infrastructure is weaker. According to a 2024 study published by the Global Alliance for Tobacco Control

(GATC) with support of the NCD Alliance³⁸, global spending on NCDs is only about 1-2% of development assistance for health, far below the levels needed to address this growing health burden.

The reliance on multi-bi financing also affects the capacity of multilateral organizations like WHO to respond to emerging health threats with flexibility. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the organization faced criticism for its slow response, partly due to the constraints posed by its earmarked funding, which limited its ability to pivot resources quickly to address the evolving crisis³⁹. Without sufficient core funding, WHO struggled to support the broader health system infrastructure in many low-income countries, which was crucial in mounting an effective pandemic response⁴⁰.

While multi-bi financing enables donors to fund priority projects, it creates challenges for global health governance by undermining the autonomy and capacity of multilateral institutions to set comprehensive health agendas. The imbalance between earmarked and core funding not only limits organizations like the WHO from addressing long-term systemic health issues but also raises concerns about the sustainability and equity of global health initiatives, particularly in the Global South. To rectify this, there is an urgent need for increased core contributions that would allow WHO and similar organizations to operate with greater flexibility and effectiveness in tackling global health challenges.

THE ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY AND ADVOCACY GROUPS

Civil society organizations (CSOs) and advocacy groups play a crucial role in shaping health priorities in the Global South. In India, CSOs have been instrumental in pushing for health equity and accountability in government health policies. Organizations such as the Public Health Foundation of India (PHFI) and Jan Swasthya Abhiyan (JSA) have been vocal in advocating for stronger public health systems and universal health coverage. The JSA's 2024 manifesto opens thus – “Our Health, Our Right! – Right to Healthcare legislation must be passed to ensure guaranteed availability of free quality treatment of all conditions, in close proximity to place of residence. Expand, improve & strengthen public healthcare infrastructure to provide such essential care. Denial, delay and incomplete treatment to be strictly prevented”⁴¹.

However, the influence of CSOs in global health agenda-setting is often limited by the dominance of international actors. According to a 2023 study by Gostin, Friedman and Finch⁴², while civil society participation in global health forums has increased, their influence is often marginalized by more powerful stakeholders, such as philanthropic foundations and international organizations. This has led to calls for greater inclusivity and transparency in the global health governance process.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the role of CSOs became even more critical. In India, grassroots organizations played a key role in providing healthcare services and raising awareness about public health measures, particularly in underserved areas⁴³. However, their contributions were often overshadowed by the larger international response, including the efforts of organizations such as WHO and Gavi⁴⁴.

INTERNATIONAL NORMS AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORKS

The global health agenda is influenced by a complex web of international norms and institutional frameworks, with organizations like WHO, the World Bank, and the GFTAM playing pivotal roles. These organizations operate within a broader

geopolitical context where the interests of powerful states, private donors and philanthrocapitalists increasingly shape priorities in the Global South.

For example, the World Bank has become a central player in health systems strengthening and universal health coverage (UHC) initiatives across the Global South. In India, the World Bank has supported the Pradhan Mantri-Ayushman Bharat Health Infrastructure Mission (PM-ABHIM), launched in October 2021, which aims to strengthen public healthcare infrastructure across India through a loan of US\$ 1 billion⁴⁵. However, the World Bank's emphasis on financial sustainability and cost-effectiveness has raised concerns about underfunding essential health services, especially for marginalized populations⁴⁶.

Similarly, the WHO has played a key role in shaping global health norms, particularly through its leadership in infectious disease control and health emergencies. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the WHO's efforts to coordinate vaccine distribution through the COVAX initiative were instrumental in ensuring some level of global access to vaccines. As of early 2023, COVAX had distributed nearly 2 billion doses of COVID-19 vaccines to 146 participating economies⁴⁷. However, the WHO's limited resources—due to its reliance on voluntary contributions, which account for more than 80% of its budget (WHO, 2023c)—have constrained its ability to address the broader, long-term health needs of LMICs. The pandemic exposed these limitations, with the WHO struggling to fully address health system resilience in these regions. As global health challenges extend beyond immediate crises, there is a growing recognition of the need for increased core funding to enable the WHO to operate with more autonomy and long-term impact.

GFTAM has also made significant contributions to the health landscape, particularly in combating HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and malaria. Since its inception in 2002, GFTAM has saved over 65 million lives through its targeted interventions⁴⁸. However, as GFTAM continues to focus on disease-specific interventions, critics argue that this approach can overshadow the importance of strengthening health systems as a whole, which is essential for sustainable health outcomes, especially in fragile settings⁴⁹.

The intersection of geopolitical interests, financial dependencies and institutional priorities creates both opportunities and challenges in the Global South's health agenda. As private actors such as philanthrocapitalists (e.g., the BMGF) and bilateral donors increase their influence in global health, questions arise about the alignment of their priorities with the needs of low-income populations. The Gates Foundation, for instance, has been a major player in polio eradication efforts, but its focus on vertical programs has raised concerns about the neglect of broader health systems that require strengthening⁵⁰.

In summary, while international organizations like WHO, the World Bank, and GFTAM play crucial roles in shaping global health norms, their operations are deeply intertwined with geopolitical forces and funding constraints that often complicate long-term health equity goals in the Global South. Ensuring that these institutions have both the resources and the autonomy to prioritize sustainable health systems strengthening is essential for achieving equitable health outcomes.

GLOBAL HEALTH UNDER TRUMP 2.0

Sustainable health systems strengthening faces a further challenge with the second Trump presidency which has profoundly reshaped the global health landscape. His focus on nationalism and skepticism of multilateralism has further fragmented global efforts to address health inequities. The second Trump presidency's executive orders

to cut foreign aid, freeze USAID programs, and withdraw from the WHO in 2025 carry profound implications for global health. The U.S. historically accounts for the largest share of global health assistance, and these measures have created an estimated \$11–13 billion shortfall, directly threatening the sustainability of HIV, tuberculosis, and malaria interventions across the Global South⁵¹. The withdrawal from the WHO could possibly result in a 21% reduction in the organization's biennial budget, undermining pandemic preparedness, vaccine distribution, and polio eradication initiatives⁵². Further, in 2025, preliminary estimates from the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation⁵³ indicate that Development Assistance for Health (DAH) declined to \$39.1 billion, marking its lowest level in over 15 years. This represents a reduction of more than 20% compared to 2024. For context, current DAH is less than half of what it was at the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2021, when unprecedented resources were mobilized globally to support countries during the health emergency.

As a result, countries such as Nigeria, Bangladesh, and India face heightened risks of setbacks in immunization coverage and maternal–child health outcomes due to reduced donor flows, while Brazil and South Africa confront gaps in infectious disease and health systems financing. Although China and the European Union have pledged to increase contributions, these compensatory efforts are insufficient to fully offset U.S. disengagement, marking a shift toward a more fragmented and regionally driven global health governance system that may weaken coordinated responses to future global health crises.

DISCUSSION: POWER DYNAMICS AND INEQUITIES IN GLOBAL HEALTH GOVERNANCE

The global health architecture is characterized by significant power imbalances, with a small number of powerful actors—governments, international organizations and philanthropic foundations—exerting disproportionate influence over health priorities. These power dynamics often result in the marginalization of the Global South, where health policies are shaped by external actors rather than local needs.

Philanthrocapitalism, in particular, has raised concerns about accountability and inclusivity in global health governance. While organizations like BMGF and Gavi have made significant contributions to improving health outcomes in the Global South, their focus on short-term, high-visibility interventions can undermine long-term health systems strengthening. Moreover, the lack of transparency in their decision-making processes raises questions about whose interests are being served.

In the case of India, the influence of philanthrocapitalist organizations has been both positive and negative. While these organizations have helped to accelerate progress in areas such as polio eradication and vaccine distribution, their priorities have sometimes diverged from national health needs. This highlights the importance of ensuring that global health funding is aligned with national health strategies and that local stakeholders, including civil society organizations and marginalized communities, are meaningfully involved in the agenda-setting process.

CONCLUSION

The dynamics of global health agenda-setting in the Global South are shaped by a complex interplay of political, economic and social factors. Philanthrocapitalist organizations, while contributing to health innovation and funding, also pose challenges to the transparency and inclusivity of the global health governance process.

In India, as in other parts of the Global South, the influence of external actors has shaped national health policies in ways that are not always aligned with local needs.

Under Trump 2.0, the U.S. retreat from multilateral health engagement—through cuts to USAID, reductions in foreign aid, and withdrawal from the WHO—has disrupted established funding streams and weakened the role of multilateral institutions in agenda-setting. This vacuum has shifted influence toward emerging donors, regional blocs, and private foundations, further fragmenting the global health governance landscape and especially affecting countries in the Global South.

To ensure that global health governance promotes health equity and social justice, it is essential to prioritize the voices of national governments, civil society organizations, and marginalized communities in the agenda-setting process. By adopting more inclusive and transparent approaches, global health actors can work together to address health disparities and build stronger, more resilient health systems in the Global South.

The next phase of global health governance must be marked by collective action, accountability and a commitment to health equity. Only by refocusing global health priorities to center the needs of vulnerable populations can we achieve the goals of universal health coverage and sustainable development.

This paper provided an analysis of the changing dynamics of global health agenda-setting in the Global South, with a particular focus on India. By exploring the roles of various stakeholders, the paper has underscored the importance of inclusive approaches that prioritize marginalized communities. As the global health landscape continues to evolve, it is imperative that all stakeholders work together to promote health equity and social justice for all.

Vivek N.D. is Adjunct Faculty, School of Legal Studies and Governance, Vidyashilp University, Bangalore, India. He has a PhD in Political Science from the University of Hyderabad. He specialises in global health governance, development issues, and non-traditional areas of international relations in relation to Asia and Africa.

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